

Plan of Top.

Side Elevation.

No. 3 'Āsana' Slab at Kantalāi on the Trincomalee railway trace. Now in Anurādhapura.

Diagram of the Kantalāi gal-āsana. Published in: Wickremasinghe, Don Martino de Zilva. (1912-27). 'No. 42. (Reg. No. 3.) Kantalāi Gal-Āsana Inscription of Kitti Nissaṅka-Malla (1187-1196 A.D.),' *Epigraphia Zeylanica* 2, p. 283.